

Comparative Analysis of MDA and Serum Minerals in Patients with Overt and Subclinical HypothyroidismAnil Chandra¹, Dr. Shreya Nigoshkar²¹PhD Scholar, Department of Biochemistry, Index Medical College Hospital & Research Centre, Indore (M.P.)²Head & Professor, Department of Biochemistry, Index Medical College Hospital & Research Centre, Indore (M.P.)

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Abstract:

Hypothyroidism is a prevalent thyroid gland disorder where the gland fails to meet the body's demand for thyroid hormones, specifically triiodothyronine (T3) and thyroxine (T4). Hypothyroidism is categorized into overt (OH) and subclinical (SbH) forms. Overt hypothyroidism is characterized by elevated thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) levels and reduced T4 levels, whereas subclinical hypothyroidism presents with elevated TSH levels but normal T4 levels. The objective of this study is to assess the levels of malondialdehyde (MDA) and certain minerals—calcium, magnesium, and phosphorus—in patients diagnosed with SbH and OH. A total of 100 patients from index medical college Indore participated in the study, with half diagnosed with OH and the other half with SbH. The study also included 50 healthy controls of comparable age, and all three groups comprised 50% males and 50% females. Anthropometric examinations revealed significant ($p < 0.05$) alterations in body mass index (BMI) and waist-to-hip ratio (WHpR) among the control, OH, and SbH groups.

MDA levels were significantly elevated in hypothyroidism patients, with OH patients exhibiting the highest levels. SbH patients showed significantly ($p < 0.05$) lower MDA levels compared to OH patients but significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher levels compared to the control group. Levels of magnesium and phosphorus were significantly ($p < 0.05$) elevated in OH patients compared to SbH patients and the control group, while the levels in SbH patients were not significantly different ($p > 0.05$) from the control group. Conversely, serum calcium levels were significantly ($p < 0.05$) reduced in OH patients compared to both SbH patients and controls, with no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) between SbH patients and the control group. Additionally, MDA was found to be significantly ($p < 0.05$) correlated with WHpR in OH patients. Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) analysis demonstrated the utility of MDA in prognosing OH and SbH with excellent sensitivity. In conclusion, the increase in MDA levels due to lipid peroxidation may contribute to the progression of subclinical hypothyroidism to overt hypothyroidism.

Keywords--Hypothyroidism, MDA, oxidative stress.

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Introduction

Hypothyroidism is a common condition affecting the thyroid gland (ThG) [1]. It is a chronic disorder where the ThG fails to produce adequate amounts of thyroid hormones, triiodothyronine (T3) and thyroxine (T4) [2]. Normally, the ThG is stimulated by thyroid stimulating hormone (TSH), which is secreted by the pituitary gland [3, 4]. In response to this stimulation, the ThG releases T4 and T3 into the bloodstream in a ratio of approximately 10:1 [5]. These thyroid hormones interact with various cells throughout the body, delivering critical signals that drive essential metabolic processes [6].

Hypothyroidism affects around 2% of adult women, with primary hypothyroidism accounting for about 95% of cases, particularly prevalent in females over the age of 60. It is nearly ten times less common in

men than in women [7]. This condition generally results from either insufficient iodine intake [8] or autoimmune issues, such as Hashimoto's disease [9]. Overt hypothyroidism (OH) occurs when the ThG produces very low levels of T4 despite high levels of TSH stimulation [10]. Another form, subclinical hypothyroidism (SbH), occurs when the ThG produces adequate T4, but under elevated TSH levels [11].

Free radicals and reactive oxygen species (ROS) play a crucial role in metabolic processes in biological systems [12]. Disruptions in these metabolic processes can lead to an increase in ROS levels [13,16]. Among the cellular macromolecules impacted by elevated ROS levels are lipids, particularly unsaturated fatty acids [17, 18]. This

process, known as lipid peroxidation, can lead to cell death through apoptosis and necrosis [19]. Malondialdehyde (MDA), a by product of lipid peroxidation, is often used as a biomarker for oxidative stress [20, 21].

Minerals are essential for numerous biological functions in living organisms [22]. Among the most important minerals found in relatively high concentrations in the human body are calcium (Ca), magnesium (Mg), and phosphorus (P) [23]. Altered serum levels of these minerals have been associated with various disorders in humans [24,26]. The main objective of this study is to examine the relationship between oxidative stress and the progression of primary hypothyroidism by measuring MDA levels in patients with OH and SbH. Additionally, the study aims to assess the potential of using MDA as a prognostic marker for hypothyroidism and its correlation with Ca, Mg, and P levels.

Material & Methods

The study has included 100 patients with primary hypothyroidism disease collected from index medical college Indore. According to their diagnosis, patients were divided into two groups, OH and SbH, each group was contained 50 subjects with age range 20-59 year. Each subject was followed a weight, height and hip measurement for the calculation of body mass index (BMI) and waist to hip ration (WHpR). Blood samples were collected then, and centrifuged (1500xg for 10 min) to separate the serum. The serum samples were stored at -20 °C until analyses.

The serum of each sample was analyzed for TSH, T3, T4, MDA, Ca, Mg, and P. The evaluation of MDA in serum was performed by using the spectrophotometric method of Bengel and Aust [27].

Statistical analyses

The Statistical Process for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26 software and Excel 2016 were used to examine the data.

Results

The demographic presentation of age was non-significantly ($p>0.05$) different among control (37.85 ± 8.67 year), SbH (38.73 ± 11.03 year) and OH subjects (38.13 ± 11.67 year). Also, BMI was observed to be significantly higher ($p<0.05$) in OH (27.85 ± 2.72 kg/m²) and SbH subjects (25.73 ± 2.67 kg/m²) compared to control (23.02 ± 2.12 kg/m²). The level of TSH was significantly elevated ($p<0.05$) in OH (16.88 ± 6.02 mIU/L) and SbH (12.2 ± 2.04 mIU/L) compared to control (1.36 ± 0.66 mIU/L). The level of MDA was significantly ($p<0.05$) elevated in OH (1.61 ± 0.61 μmol/L) and SbH (1.40 ± 0.33 μmol/L) patients compared to control (0.85 ± 0.10 μmol/L). Serum Ca level was

significantly reduced ($p<0.05$) in OH (8.0 ± 0.59 mg/dL) compared to SbH (8.22 ± 0.22 mg/dL) and control (8.30 ± 0.40 mg/dL). Furthermore, Mg level was significantly higher ($p<0.05$) in OH (2.48 ± 0.61 mg/dL) compared to SbH (2.33 ± 0.37 mg/dL) and control (2.07 ± 0.12 mg/dL). Also, P level was increased significantly ($p<0.05$) in OH (6.26 ± 1.78 mg/dL) compared to SbH (3.73 ± 0.38 mg/dL) and control (3.58 ± 0.39 mg/dL).

Discussion

Hypothyroidism is known to produce various clinical symptoms due to reduced metabolic rates [6]. It has been documented that primary hypothyroidism can be classified into overt hypothyroidism (OH) and subclinical hypothyroidism (SbH) based on clinical presentation. In this study, SbH was defined by T4 levels above 5 μg/dL and TSH levels exceeding 5 mIU/L. Conversely, OH was characterized by T4 levels below 5 μg/dL and TSH levels over 5 mIU/L. The differentiation did not consider T3 levels, as T4 is the predominant thyroid hormone in circulation, which is subsequently converted to its active form (T3) within target cells. This approach aligns with other studies [28, 29]. Anthropometric data revealed that both OH and SbH patients were overweight. This outcome is expected due to the influence of thyroid hormones. T3, in particular, plays a role in stimulating lipolysis in target cells; hence, reduced T3 levels can lead to fat accumulation in the body [30], causing an imbalance in energy intake and expenditure, which eventually leads to weight gain [31, 32]. Furthermore, OH has been suggested to contribute to weight gain by increasing mucin deposition in the skin and other tissues, as well as promoting water and salt retention [33]. Clinical evidence also suggests that even mild thyroid dysfunction, such as subclinical hypothyroidism, is linked to significant weight fluctuations [34], although this relationship is not entirely understood. MDA levels were found to be significantly elevated in both OH and SbH patients. Torun et al. [35] observed similar increases in MDA levels in these patient groups, attributing the rise in oxidative stress in SbH to changes in lipid metabolism. Other studies have also reported elevated lipid peroxidation in hypothyroidism [36-38]. The precise mechanism behind the increased oxidative stress in hypothyroidism remains unclear, though it is believed that mitochondrial dysfunction may play a role, as ROS production can be influenced by the metabolic state through the mitochondrial respiratory chain [39]. Several studies have linked mitochondrial dysfunction to OH [40, 42] and SbH [43, 44]. Additionally, oxidative stress in hypothyroidism may be exacerbated by a compromised antioxidant defense system, as several studies have shown a reduction in specific antioxidants [45,47]. Moreover, MDA levels

positively correlated with WHpR in OH patients, suggesting that overweight status, another contributor to oxidative stress, enhances ROS production while diminishing antioxidant levels [48,50]. The study also revealed that OH patients experienced decreased serum calcium levels alongside increased magnesium and phosphorus levels. Similar findings were reported by Şim Şek et al. [51], who attributed these mineral imbalances to thyroid hormone dysfunction. T4 regulates calcium levels by facilitating its release into the extracellular space, and reduced T4 circulation in hypothyroidism limits extracellular Calcium release [52]. Reported no significant alterations in these minerals in hypothyroidism.

Conclusions

The study results revealed a significant increase in MDA levels in both OH and SbH, suggesting systemic oxidative stress. MDA demonstrated high sensitivity in predicting the prognosis of these conditions. Additionally, the progressive rise in MDA levels from healthy individuals to SbH patients, and ultimately to OH patients, may suggest a clear trajectory indicating the potential progression of SbH to OH over time. Further research is needed to explore this pathway in more detail.

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